

A STUDY OF THE PERCEPTION OF B.ED STUDENTS TOWARDS CULTURE

Dr. Rukmini Jamdar,

Assistant Professor,

Seva sadan's College of Education, Ulhasnagar.

Introduction

Culture is the backbone of any Indian family. The family members follow the culture inherited from the ancestors and our forefathers. It needs to be conserved and passed on to the next generation. What are the constituents or elements of culture? In simple terms, elements of culture are religion, dressing style, diet pattern, way of living, language, celebration of different festivals etc.

Each one of us practice our culture since generations and pass on the same culture to the next generation. Culture is preserved as treasure given by our ancestors. Every community have their own culture which is cherished by them. In 21st century we do see some change in culture with terms to dressing style, eating habits, way of living,celebration of different festivals etc.

Importance of Culture: it is since year that we have been practicing the cultures so that the current generation identifies the different elements of culture. It is also important to know the culture because of the varied nature. The following of the culture sets tone to remarkable beginning. Every generation learns the aesthetic beauty of their culture, only if they know their culture.to set an identity to ones community, to make them distinct from other communities, we should know our culture.

Keeping in mind the need and importance of culture the researcher conducted a survey to find **the perception of teacher trainees towards the culture.**

Need for the study: the researcher wanted to find out how the teacher trainees who would be an effective teacher perceive culture. In turn they would carry the perceptions in their future to the students of school who need to know different cultures and how well can they be practiced in their era. Hence the need for this research. Moreover whether there is rigidity among the women teacher trainees towards their culture or do they practice some elements of culture o other communities as well, the researcher wanted to study.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To study the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture.
- 2) To compare the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of different communities.
- 3) To compare the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of marital status.

Hypotheses :

- 1) There is no significant difference between the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of different communities
- 2) There is no significant difference between the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of marital status.

Method used: The researcher undertook the descriptive survey method for this research.

Sample : In all 60 women teacher trainees were selected for the study.

Sampling : Random sampling technique was used by the researcher. Care was taken that the sample included all the types communities among the women teacher trainees from the B.Ed college.

Tool used for the research : The researcher prepared a questionnaire of 24 questions with two options namely, “yes” and ‘no’. All the questions were closed ended questions. The content validity was given to experts, and the reliability test was also administered.

Analysis of data (objective wise)

1) Table no.1 showing the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture.

s.no.	Description	Yes %	No %
1	I pray to the almighty everyday before, and after meals	78.3	21.7
2	I do not fast on religious occasions	36.7	63.3
3	I enjoy eating food from other community	95.0	5.0
4	I learn new recipes made by people from other communities	100.0	-
5	I strictly follow diet cooked by my community	16.7	83.3
6	I do not try new dressing styles worn by women of other community	41.7	58.3
7	I do not participate in festivals celebrated by other communities	28.3	71.7
8	I follow rituals of my community strictly.	61.7	38.3
9	I do not visit religious places of other community	40.0	60.0
10	I speak and respect only my mother tongue	10	90
11	I do not enjoy languages of other community	8.3	91.7
12	I do not drink water from people of other community	18.3	81.7
13	I recite prayers from my religious book	76.7	23.3
14	I like to visit my friends from other community during festivals	85	15
15	I do not do my routine schedule without taking bath	50	50
16	I celebrate festivals of my community only	23.3	76.7
17	I buy new dresses during the festivals	76.7	23.3
18	I do not watch dance programmes of other communities	5	95
19	I like to learn new languages	100	-
20	I do not light the lamp in the evening regularly before reciting prayers	16.7	83.3
21	I eat only vegetarian food	26.7	73.3
22	I do not cook non veg food in my home	30	70
23	I do not include onion and garlic in my food	10	90
24	I do not like to visit my friends house of other communities	8.3	91.7

From the above table no.1 it is seen that all the women teacher trainees like to learn recipes from other communities and also like to learn new languages.95% of the women teacher trainees enjoy eating food from other communities,75% celebrate festivals of other communities,91.7% enjoy languages of other communities,95% watch programmes of other communities,83% women teacher trainees do not follow strict diet cooked by their community and 91.7% like to visit their friends house of other communities.

2) Table No.2 showing the Perception of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of religion

Religion	N	Mean	Std. deviation	F-value	Sig
Muslim	14	11.43	2.50	1.947	0.132
Hindu	37	10.27	3.44		

Christian	7	10.57	1.40	Not significant at 0.05 level
Buddhism	2	6.00	3.12	

From the above table no.2 it is found out that the obtained F-value (ANOVA) is 1.947 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of religion.

3) Table No.3 showing the Perception of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of marital status

Marital status	N	Mean	Std deviation	t-value	Level of significance at 0.051
Married	21	10.38	3.61	0.095	Not significant
Unmarried	39	10.46	2.87		

From the above table no.3 it is found out that the obtained t-value is 0.095 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of women teacher trainees towards culture on the basis of marital status.

Conclusions : Women interpret their culture on the basis of various parameters like love for language, food, dressing style, celebration of festivals, religious outlook etc. in the 21st century one can observe the flexibility in terms respect for other's culture by way of participating, sharing and caring for the people of other community. Moreover the perceptions of culture are not varied in terms of different community.

It is truly said that India is a land of diversity. but united as a whole nation.

References :

- Best J and Khan J(2002), Research in Education, New Delhi: Prentice hall of India.
 Digumarti Bhaskara Rao, Women , Educationand Empowerment, Discovery publishing House, New Delhi.2004
 Menu Agarwal,Women Empowerment- Today's Vision for Tomorrow's Mission Mahamaya Publishing House, New Delhi,2007
 UNESCO,the education and advancement of women,1970.
 B.M.Sharma, Women and Education, Commonwealth publishers New Delhi.2005.
 M.Lakshmikumari,-the role of women in society, Sterling Publishers private limited.